

A STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC DIMENSION OF VERB PHRASEOLOGICAL UNIT IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This article presents a comparative study of the structural-semantic features of verb phraseological units (VPUs) in English and Russian languages. VPUs are a pivotal component of phraseological studies, offering insights into the linguistic and cultural fabric of languages. This study aims to elucidate the complexities and nuances inherent in VPUs, providing language learners and linguists with a deeper understanding of these expressions.

Key words: phraseology, verb phraseological units, English language, Russian language, structural features, semantic features, language learning.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va rus tillaridagi fe'l frazeologik birliklarning (FFBlarning) tarkibiy-semantik xususiyatlarini qiyosiy o'rganish keltirilgan. FFBlar frazeologik tadqiqotlarning asosiy komponenti bo'lib, tillarning lingvistik va madaniy tuzilishi haqida tushuncha beradi. Ushbu tadqiqot FFBlarga xos bo'lgan murakkabliklar va nuanslarni tushuntirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, til o'rganuvchilar va tilshunoslarga ushbu iboralarni chuqurroq tushunishni ta'minlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: frazeologiya, fe'l frazeologik birliklari, ingliz tili, rus tili, tarkibiy xususiyatlari, semantik xususiyatlari, til o'rganish.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлено сравнительное исследование структурно-семантических особенностей глагольных фразеологических единиц (ГФЕ) в английском и русском языках. ГФЕ являются ключевым компонентом фразеологических исследований, позволяющим глубже понять лингвистическую и культурную структуру языков. Это исследование направлено на то, чтобы прояснить сложности и нюансы, присущие ГФЕ, и помочь изучающим язык и лингвистам глубже понять эти выражения.

Ключевые слова: фразеология, глагольные фразеологизмы, английский язык, русский язык, структурные особенности, семантические особенности, изучение языка.

Phraseology, the study of fixed expressions such as idioms, proverbs, and collocations, is a fascinating domain that bridges linguistic structure and cultural

semantics. Among these, verb phraseological units (VPUs) are particularly intriguing due to their syntactic flexibility and semantic richness. This article delves into the structural-semantic characteristics of VPUs in English and Russian, highlighting both the commonalities and unique aspects shaped by the languages' distinct grammatical and cultural frameworks.

Phraseological units, particularly those containing verbs, are integral to the expressiveness and idiomatic richness of a language. In English and Russian, VPUs serve not only as linguistic tools but also as carriers of cultural and historical significance. This study examines the structural patterns and semantic properties of VPUs in both languages, highlighting their implications for language acquisition and translation.

The structure of VPUs in English often follow a predictable structure, typically consists of a verb followed by a noun or prepositional phrase (e. g. , “break the ice”). These units maintain their grammatical flexibility, allowing for modifications in tense, aspect, and voice while preserving their idiomatic meaning. However, the semantic integrity of the phraseological unit remains intact across these transformations. Russian VPUs, characterized by their inflectional morphology, exhibit a similar syntactic pattern but with a greater degree of morphological variation. Russian VPUs exhibit a similar structural pattern, with the verb preceding other elements. However, due to the rich inflectional system of the Russian language, these units can undergo more extensive morphological changes while maintaining their phraseological meaning (e. g. , “бить баклуши” [to idle]). Semantically, English VPUs often draw from cultural or historical contexts, rendering their meanings non-literal and metaphorical. Russian VPUs share this figurative nature, with many expressions derived from folklore and daily life. The semantic interpretation of VPUs in both languages requires an understanding of underlying metaphorical and symbolic associations.

A comparative analysis reveals that both English and Russian utilize metaphor and metonymy in VPUs, yet the specific expressions reflect the distinct cultural narratives of each language community. This comparison underscores the importance of cultural context in the interpretation of VPUs and the challenges it poses for language learners and translators. Comparing English and Russian VPUs reveals both similarities and differences. Both languages use metaphor and metonymy as primary semantic mechanisms in the creation of VPUs. However, the specific expressions often reflect the cultural and historical narratives unique to each language community. For instance, while English has the VPU “spill the beans” to denote

revealing a secret, Russian uses “проболтаться” (to blab), which lacks the bean imagery. Such differences underscore the cultural specificity of VPUs and the importance of context in their interpretation. The study of VPUs has significant implications for language learning. The complexity of VPUs can increase cognitive load, necessitating a comprehensive cultural understanding. Mastery of VPUs is often indicative of language proficiency, and their correct usage is crucial for effective communication. The challenges in translating VPUs highlight the need for finding culturally equivalent expressions or rephrasing ideas in the target language.

The structural-semantic features of VPUs in English and Russian are reflective of the intricate interplay between language structure and cultural semantics. This study contributes to the field of phraseology by providing a comparative perspective on VPUs, emphasizing their role in language learning and cross-cultural communication.

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